

Health Rights and Challenges to Tribal Population in India

¹KAILASH DONGREY, ²NAVRATI DONGREY

¹Assistant professor, ² Assistant professor

¹Department of Economics

¹Govt. Home Science P.G. College, Hoshangabad, India

Abstract:

It is stated in the preamble of WHO's contribution that "Health is a condition of total physical, mental, and social wellness and not only the absence of sickness." This definition of health is the most commonly used and should be the priority while building any nation. However, even after 75 years of independence, India has failed to bridge the divide between tribal and non-tribal communities. The obligation to uphold social and economic fairness was placed on the state by the framers of the Constitution. The constitutional provisions found in Articles 38, 39(e), 42, 47, and 48A of Part IV of the Indian Constitution ensure that the government is required to establish and maintain environments conducive to health. However, it remains unclear whether these government healthcare policies, programmes, and goals are reaching the underprivileged, particularly scheduled tribes.

The Human Happiness Index (HHI), which includes health as a major component of individual well-being, provides a framework for evaluating the success of a nation's development policies. In tribal regions, where healthcare services are often inadequate or inaccessible, the resulting poor health outcomes directly affect the overall happiness and quality of life of the population. This gap in healthcare delivery reduces life satisfaction among tribal communities, thereby negatively impacting India's overall ranking on the HHI. Thus, this paper will focus on issues such as healthcare policies, difficulties with implementation, state participation, features of healthcare, flaws in governmental policies, and methods to enhance the way healthcare is provided in tribal communities. Improving tribal healthcare is essential not only for fulfilling constitutional obligations but also for enhancing the nation's overall happiness and well-being.

Keywords: Right to health, tribal population, constitution, healthcare, policies, Human Happiness Index

1. Introduction

With 8.6% of the population being tribal¹, India is having a hard time closing the healthcare gap between tribal and non-tribal residents. Massive disease burden affects the tribal people, including communicable and non-communicable illnesses, hunger, mental illness, and addictions exacerbated by poor health-seeking behavior. Based on the 2011 census, 104 million tribal people are living in the Indian subcontinent who can be divided into 698 different tribes², taking into account sociocultural factors and keeping in mind their way of life for the advancement and preservation of tribals. The recommendations of a tribal health expert committee in response to growing requirements with the aim at bridging the

¹ Dileep Mavalankar, *Doctors for Tribal Areas: Issues and Solutions*, 41 INDIAN J COMMUNITY MED 172 (2016), <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4919928/> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

² Karnika Bahuguna, *Indigenous people in India and the web of indifference*, DOWNTOEARTH, August 9, 2016, <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/coverage/governance/indigenous-people-in-india-and-the-web-of-indifference-55223> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

present difference in the health status before 2027.³ A completely different health system with distinct goals for governance and funding has been suggested.

The health of scheduled tribes is declining and failing even after they have been given policies and direction by the central government. The idea of marginalised communities is present even in tribal communities, where women and children frequently die as a result of inadequate health care, starvation, etc. One of the reasons to highlight, denying tribal people their natural rights, such as health, food, etc., is land grabbing by corporations and the government. This leads to the depletion of natural resources, which in turn threatens their ability to support themselves. For instance, in some areas of the Vishakhapatnam district along the borders of Andhra Pradesh and Odisha, a sizable portion of the population is tribal, and their sole source of subsistence is the farming of cash crops like paddy, coffee, turmeric, and spices.⁴ Tribal people in this area risk losing all means of subsistence if there are any land grabs.

The Human Development Index (HDI)⁵ and Human Happiness Index (HHI) in economics emphasize that health is one of the key indicators of a nation's overall well-being and prosperity. The text highlights the challenges faced by tribal communities in India due to inadequate healthcare, underscoring the importance of inclusive healthcare for national development. According to the HDI framework, health indicators such as life expectancy and access to medical services are critical for assessing overall human development. For the disadvantaged sections, like tribal communities, neglecting healthcare leads to poorer health outcomes, directly impacting their quality of life and, consequently, the nation's overall happiness index. A holistic and sustainable healthcare delivery system, which considers the unique socio-cultural and geographical factors of tribal communities, is essential for improving their health outcomes and contributing to the nation's economic prosperity and human happiness.

The lack of tailored healthcare solutions for tribal communities highlights the failure of the national healthcare system to consider the diversity within its population. As a result, health disparities in tribal regions remain, which not only affects the overall Human Happiness Index of the country but also impedes India's progress towards improving its HDI ranking. The connection between health and economic productivity, alongside the overall well-being of the population, is essential in the context of the Happiness Index, as poor health services reduce life satisfaction and lead to socio-economic stagnation in disadvantaged communities.

Now, the primary concerns are:

- Do tribal people still experience health and healthcare disparities concerning others almost seven decades after independence? If yes, then why?
- How can this gap be quickly bridged?

2. Present scenario: the disease burdened tribals

Tribal people are not included in the nation's socioeconomic mainstream, which inevitably leads to their lower levels of economic and educational success (41% Illiteracy and 41% Below Poverty Line)⁶; an existence usually marred by material deprivation and limited access to public amenities and services. Furthermore, harmful cultural practices and social attitudes that are frequently still practised have an obvious impact on people's health and health-seeking behaviour.

³ M Mohan Kumar, Vineet Kumar Pathak & Manisha Ruikar, *Tribal population in India: A public health challenge and road to future*, 9 J FAMILY MED PRIM CARE 508 (2020), <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC7113978/> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

⁴ DEPARTMENT OF AGRICULTURE, VISAKHAPATNAM, *Agriculture | Visakhapatnam District, Government of Andhra Pradesh | India*, DISTRICT VISAKHAPATNAM, <https://visakhapatnam.ap.gov.in/agriculture/> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

⁵ United Nations Development Programme, *Human Development Report 2020: The Next Frontier—Human Development and the Anthropocene* (Dec. 15, 2020).

⁶ Kumar, Pathak, and Ruikar, *supra* note 3.

In terms of several health indices, the tribal population trails behind the national average, with women and children being the most at risk.

Only 15% of ANC visits are completed, and the overall fertility rate is 2.5%. Only 56% of youngsters have received all recommended vaccinations, resulting in an IMR of 44.4% and an underage mortality rate of 57.2%.⁷

42% of children are reported to be underweight, and 77% of underweight children are anaemic. According to reports, hunger and child fatalities occur in waves, primarily during the rainy seasons.

A vicious loop exists whereby over 50% of adolescent ST girls have a BMI below 18.5 and roughly 65% of tribal women (aged 15 to 49) experience anaemia (compared to 47% of non-tribal women).⁸ In comparison to 56% and 30% of non-tribal men, more than 72% of tribal men aged 15 to 54 use cigarettes and more than 50% drink alcohol.⁹

3. Shocking Cases

A. Miscarriage due to lack of nutrition

According to a survey by NRHM, over 100 newborn deaths and miscarriages in the Attapadi region of Kerala, where there are about 88 tribal hamlets, were caused by a lack of nourishing food and sufficient prenatal care, and the majority of the tribal infants were underweight. The failure of welfare programmes and the alienation of thousands of hectares of agricultural land by non-tribal people, whose possession has since been dispersed, are the main causes of starvation and the absence of vital health care facilities.¹⁰

B. Illegal clinical trial on tribal girls.

Poor and remote tribal people have been used as "guinea pigs" by many pharmaceutical companies. As many as 25,000 girls who were recruited for cervical cancer vaccine clinical trials were vaccinated in Gujarat and Andhra Pradesh between 2007 and 2012; this was done without the consent of the parents and in violation of the Medical Research Council of India's ethical standards. Several tribal girls and boys died as a result within a week.¹¹

C. Forceful sterilization of women

There have been reported deaths and injuries of tribal women who have undergone sterilisation, where 14 tribal women died, including 2 women from the Bagia community, which falls under a particularly vulnerable tribal group and has been adopted by the President of India for protection. Women were targeted in a government policy under the guise of population control, and they have to pay the heavy price while their men are also reasonable for family planning. In the Chhattisgarh private hospital, where they received funding from the RSBY National Health Insurance Scheme Package, nearly 7000 women were compelled to have their uteruses removed over the course of 30 months.¹²

⁷Annual Report 2017-18, GOVERNMENT OF INDIA MINISTRY OF TRIBAL AFFAIRS, <https://tribal.nic.in/writereaddata/AnnualReport/AR2017-18.pdf>. (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

⁸ Jai Prakash Narain, *Health of tribal populations in India: How long can we afford to neglect?* - PMC, 149 INDIAN J MED RES. 313, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6607830/> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

⁹ V.G. Rao et al., *Pulmonary tuberculosis - a health problem amongst Saharia tribe in Madhya Pradesh*, 141 INDIAN J MED RES 630 (2015), <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4510762/> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

¹⁰ Swarajya Staff, *The Starving Tribals Of Kerala's Attappady: A Shocking Case Of Government Apathy*, SWARAJYA, <https://swarajyamag.com/politics/the-starving-tribals-of-keralas-attappady-a-shocking-case-of-government-apathy> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

¹¹ SAMAWOMENSHEALTH, *Trial and Error: Ethical Violations of HPV Vaccination Trials in India* | Sama: Resource Group for Women and Health, SAMA, <https://samawomenshealth.wordpress.com/2010/05/17/trial-and-error-ethical-violations-of-hpv-vaccination-trials-in-india/> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

¹² Jason Burke, *India mass sterilisation: women were 'forced' into camps, say relatives* | India | *The Guardian*, THE GUARDIAN, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2014/nov/12/india-sterilisation-deaths-women-forced-camps-relatives> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

4. Health-seeking behaviour and healthcare delivery system

Purely 6% of the tribal women who participated in a 2000 study¹³ in Odisha, India, used only allopathic treatment, whereas 49% received traditional medicine, primarily from local quacks. Furthermore, 11% of them believe that no one can prevent disease since it is God's will.¹⁴ If the residents of that area do not use the healthcare facility that is there, it cannot be said that they are in good health. Numerous studies have revealed that the tribal population uses contemporary healthcare services at a very low rate. Therefore, there is a need for behaviour modification models to encourage people to use the advance Indian system of medicine, in addition to the provision of traditional healthcare methods.

The healthcare system and the number of specialists working in tribal regions make the burden of sickness much worse than it already is. The shortage of primary healthcare services is reported to be present in 27% of Health Sub-Centres, 40% of Primary Health Centers, and 31% of Community Health Centers throughout 29 States and Union Territories.¹⁵

The report also states the lack of specialised doctors and quality health centres in the tribal area of around 10 Indian states.

5. Government policies

The Indian Constitution has always played a crucial role in including important provisions to enhance the welfare of STs and other tribes. India is renowned for its system of discrimination, which we have ingrained among its diverse population. One prominent method of positive discrimination is taken into consideration in order to get rid of these historical discriminations, which are one of the oldest issues. The Tribal Health Plan, which involved employing 250 physicians to fill openings, had been introduced in 1992. But after four years, this objective was carried out and was now in effect.

In order to address the welfare of STs more broadly, the Government of India produced a draught National Policy on Tribes in 2006. The Nehruvian Panchasheel, which acknowledged the many difficulties that STs face in trying to preserve and advance their culture, served as the model for this policy. However, because the Nehruvian Panchasheel has been consistently incorporated into state revisions, it has certain limitations to its efficacy.

Finally, in 2013, after eleven years of programmes, the Ministries of Health and Family Welfare and Tribal Affairs created a joint Expert Committee on Tribal Health¹⁶ in acknowledgement of the need to address tribal people's health with serious and special care. The following were the goals:

- To evaluate the current state of health in tribal communities, offer solutions, create strategic directives for states, and suggest whether more resources are needed.
- To create a framework and action plan to enhance the appropriateness, accessibility, and quality of health care at national level by the tribal community.

The Expert committee has made a number of recommendations with the aim of bridging the present difference between the health status of communities by the year 2027. These suggestions mostly centre on improving the healthcare system.

¹³ Meerambika Mahapatro & A.K. Kalla, *Health seeking behaviour in a tribal setting*, 23 160 (2000).

¹⁴ Kumar, Pathak, and Ruikar, *supra* note 3.

¹⁵ (PDF) Health and Health Seeking Behaviour among Tribal Communities in India: A Socio-Cultural Perspective, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267574486_Health_and_Health_Seeking_Behaviour_among_Tribal_Communities_in_India_A_Socio-Cultural_Perspective (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

¹⁶ Mamta Verma, *Lived experiences of nurses and midwives about pregnancy and childbirth care among tribal women at secondary level health care facilities of Madhya Pradesh, India.*, 9 PUBLIC HEALTH REVIEW: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PUBLIC HEALTH RESEARCH 1 (2022), <https://publichealth.medresearch.in/index.php/ijphr/article/view/178> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

The Expert committee has identified ten distinct issues that are unique to tribal communities and has established objectives for each of these issues.

6. DPSP and right to health

The ideas of health, progress, and advancement all fit into a domino-effect equation where one thing leads to another. A country's progress toward economic and social development will undoubtedly be facilitated by a healthy population because doing so will secure people's advancement. Since obtaining political and social independence, India has recognised the absolute necessity of the right to health and access to healthcare facilities. India has traditionally seen the people as the deserving guardians of this right, with the State acting as the necessary guarantor. India, as a peace envoy for the UN, has supported a number of international accords pertaining to the right to get healthcare.

The Directive Principles of State Policy, which instruct the state to carry out and undertake tasks to ensure that the people of India have access to health services, are included in Part 4 of the Indian Constitution. Article 38 enumerates that “the state will secure a social order for the promotion of the welfare of the people.”¹⁷ One of the best ways to promote welfare is by providing affordable healthcare. Article 39(e)¹⁸ states that “the state should ensure that the health conditions of workers are not abused.” Article 41 states that “duty is imposed on the state to provide assistance to the unemployed, sick, disabled, and in old age.”¹⁹ Article 42 protects infants' and mothers' health through the maternity benefit scheme.²⁰ The majority of the measures in Article 47, which places an obligation on the state to advance public health, are already mentioned.²¹ Article 48 A provides that the “state shall endeavour to protect and impose a pollution-free environment for good health.”²²

7. Fundamental rights and the right to health

The right to health is not specifically acknowledged as a fundamental right under Part III of the Indian Constitution as a Fundamental Right. However, legal interpretation has merged this into the basic “right to life and personal liberty” under Article 21²³ and is now seen as an inherent part of “the Right to Life.” The Indian Constitution's Article 23 forbids child labour and human trafficking, which indirectly protects the Right to Health.

It is notable how the Indian Supreme Court has contributed to public health protection. The Supreme Court has stated again and time again that “the term life in Article 21 refers to a life with human dignity, not only survival or an animal existence (Francis Coralie Mullin vs The Administrator, Union Territory of Delhi²⁴).” The phrase “right to life” refers to a broad spectrum of liberties, such as the right to leisure, a liveable salary, a higher standard of living, and sanitary working conditions. Therefore, having the right to health is crucial to leading a life of dignity.

8. Judicial intervention and the right to health

In the matter of “Bandhua Mukti Morcha v Union of India”²⁵, the court outlined the parameters of Article 21 of the Constitution and declared that “everyone in this country has a fundamental right to live in dignity, free from exploitation, as guaranteed by the interpretation of Article 21 provided by this court in Francis Mullin's Case. The directing principles of state policy, in particular clauses (e) and (f) of art 39 and arts 41 and 42, give life to the right to live with the dignity that is inscribed in art 21. It must cover

¹⁷ INDIA CONST. art. 38.

¹⁸ INDIA CONST. art. 39.

¹⁹ INDIA CONST. art. 41.

²⁰ INDIA CONST. art. 42.

²¹ INDIA CONST. art. 47.

²² INDIA CONST. art. 48A,

²³ INDIA CONST. art. 21.

²⁴ AIR 1981 746

²⁵ AIR 1997 10 SCC 549

the following: maternity leave; educational facilities; fair and humane working conditions; protection of the health and strength of employees, men and women; and young children against abuse; opportunities and facilities for children to develop in a healthy manner and conditions of freedom and dignity. These are the absolute necessities in order to allow someone to live with human dignity. No state, including the federal government and all state governments, has the authority to take any action that will deny someone access to these necessities.”

In *Paschim Banga Khet Mazdoor Samity v. State of West Bengal & Ors*²⁶, the court concluded that, “in a welfare state, the government's top priority is to ensure the welfare of the populace, even as it expanded the application of Art. 21 and its mandate to provide medical care for everyone in the nation. In a welfare state, it is the responsibility of the government to ensure that the populace has access to proper medical services. By providing medical treatment to people requesting to use those facilities, the government fulfils this duty. According to Article 21, the state is required to protect each person's right to life. Thus, protecting human life is of utmost importance. The state-run government hospitals have a responsibility to provide medical care in order to preserve human life. A government hospital's failure to give prompt medical care to a patient in need of such care is a violation of the Article 21-guaranteed a patient's right to life.”

In *Paramanand Katara v. Union of India*²⁷, it was decided that “every doctor, whether practising in a government hospital or otherwise, has a duty to offer his professional services with the necessary expertise to preserve life. No state regulation or enactment of law can prevent the medical community's primary duty from being fulfilled without delay. Since the obligation is comprehensive, absolute, and paramount, any laws of procedure, whether enshrined in statutes or not, that might prevent it from being fulfilled must be disregarded.”

The Supreme Court came to the conclusion that the right to health is a basic right in *CESC Ltd. vs. Subash Chandra Bose*²⁸ by referring to international treaties. Further, it noted that being healthy involves more than just being free from illness: “The term health implies more than an absence of sickness. In addition to preventing illness, medical care and health facilities also guarantee a steady labour force for economic growth. The availability of healthcare facilities inspires workers to provide their physical and mental best in order to be productive. It makes it possible for the worker to take pleasure in the products of his job and to maintain his physical and mental alertness in order to lead a successful economic, social, and cultural life. Therefore, medical facilities are a part of social security, and just like gold-plated security, they would immediately pay for themselves through improved productivity or, at the at least, by lowering absence due to illness and other reasons.”

9. Conclusion

Healthcare has been shown to be a very effective and efficient strategy for controlling the emerging challenges that constitute a threat to health and well-being in the future as well as for addressing the major causes and hazards of ill health and well-being today. There is proof that good primary care lowers overall healthcare expenses and boosts efficiency by lowering hospital admissions: a worthwhile investment²⁹. More importantly, the poor health of the tribal population cannot be solved by the simple installation of public health care centres and sub-centres. Lack of skilled individuals to deliver high-quality healthcare is the key problem and a barrier to the spread of health services to rural and tribal areas. It is possible to teach and educate traditional healers, who typically offer the initial level of care, on how to do simple therapies and choose whether to refer patients to more specialised institutions. It is necessary

²⁶ (1996) 4 SCC 37.

²⁷ AIR 1989 SC 2039.

²⁸ AIR 1992 SC 573,585

²⁹ Primary health care, WORLD HEALTH ORGANISATION, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/primary-health-care> (last visited Sep 1, 2022).

to improve the primary healthcare system as a whole, including the supporting structures and HRH. Less educated tribal boys and girls can be trained as community health workers and inspired to work in their neighbourhood. More research is needed on the indigenous herbal treatments utilised by tribal people, and their use should be encouraged wherever it is advantageous. States must act quickly to identify the needs and priorities of their indigenous people, then set objectives and timelines to achieve those objectives using tried-and-true public health methods.

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